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FEATURES OF POLYMER IMPREGNATION IN CONCRETE

AUESBEK SULTAN TEMIRBEKULY

LESBEK AINAZYM AIZHARYKKYZY

PhD, Lecturer at the Department of Industrial, Civil, and Road Construction

M. Auezov South Kazakhstan University, Shymkent

Student of the Department of Industrial, Civil, and Road Construction

M. Auezov South Kazakhstan University, Shymkent

Аннотация. В статье представлены результаты экспериментальных исследований физико-механических свойств бетонополимеров, подтверждающие эффективность применения пропитки исходных бетонов полимерными составами. Рассмотрены способы пропитки бетонов метилметакрилатом и метилсиликонатом натрия, обеспечивающие улучшение прочностных характеристик и повышение стойкости материала к воздействию агрессивных сред. Установлено, что использование указанных пропиточных материалов способствует снижению водопоглощения, повышению плотности структуры и увеличению долговечности бетонных конструкций. Полученные результаты могут быть использованы при проектировании, реконструкции и эксплуатации строительных объектов, работающих в условиях повышенной влажности и химической агрессии.

Abstract. The article presents the results of experimental studies on the physical and mechanical properties of polymer concretes, confirming the effectiveness of impregnating base concretes with polymer compositions. Methods of concrete impregnation with methyl methacrylate and sodium methyl silicate are considered, providing improved strength characteristics and increased resistance of the material to aggressive environments. It has been established that the use of these impregnating materials contributes to reduced water absorption, increased structural density, and enhanced durability of concrete structures. The obtained results can be applied in the design, reconstruction, and operation of construction facilities operating under conditions of high humidity and chemical aggressiveness.

Keywords: impregnation, polymer, polymerization, concrete, methyl methacrylate, sodium methylsilicate, concrete polymer.

Most polymers used in construction are expensive and scarce materials; therefore, for their rational and economical use, it is necessary to properly prepare the base concrete prior to impregnation. Both full treatment of the concrete and partial treatment of the most critical areas are possible, including surface layers, locations of high-strength reinforcement, and the most highly stressed zones. Liquid polymer impregnating compositions are most commonly used, with the expectation that polymerization will occur directly within the concrete matrix. Polymerization can be carried out by various methods depending on the monomer used; however, the thermocatalytic method is the most widely applied [1, 2].

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In the thermocatalytic method, polymerization initiators are added to the monomer before its use for impregnation. After impregnating the concrete, the product or structure is heated to 70–

120 °C (depending on the type of monomer), and within a few hours the liquid monomer transforms into a solid polymer, tightly filling and effectively sealing all pores and defects in the concrete.

The resulting polymer concrete is thus a new material with its own technology, physical and mechanical properties, calculation methods, and rational fields of application. The main binding component in such composites is cement, whose pore space is partially or fully filled with the hardened polymer [3].

The main advantages of the polymer under consideration are as follows:

- Methyl methacrylate (MMA) increases the strength of concrete by several times;
- Concrete treated with MMA resins does not require repairs for up to 25 years;
- It creates a homogeneous and monolithic coating structure;
- Impregnation with methyl methacrylate-based compositions is extremely simple in practice;
- It ensures rapid adhesion to the concrete surface;
- It complies with strict environmental standards [3].

The concrete sample impregnation process consists of the following steps: drying to a moisture content of 1%, impregnation, and polymerization.

The concrete sample impregnation process consists of the following steps: drying to a moisture content of 1%, impregnation, and polymerization. For drying, samples were placed in a drying oven, with preliminary weighing to determine moisture content. The dried samples were then immersed in the monomer, allowing complete penetration. After two hours, the samples were removed and heated using calorifiers at 65–90 °C to accelerate polymerization in the pore space.

Methyl methacrylate and sodium methyl silicate were used for concrete impregnation. These low-viscosity polymers are capable of penetrating deeply into the concrete matrix. The test results are presented in Table 1.

Properties of Concrete	Polymer Concrete	Base Concrete
CEM II/A-S 42.5 N cement Methyl Methacrylate		
Compressive strength, 28 days		
Impregnation duration:		
• 30 minutes	62,1 MPa	58,4 MPa
• 90 minutes	67,2 MPa	
• 120 minutes	74,3 MPa	
CEM II/A-S 42.5 N cement Sodium methylsilicate		
Compressive strength at 28 days		
Impregnation duration:		
• 30 minutes	59,3 MPa	53,6 MPa
• 90 minutes	62,4 MPa	
• 120 minutes	66,3 MPa	

To determine the properties of polymer concrete, experiments were carried out on cubic samples measuring 7 cm, prepared from fine-grained concrete based on **Sebryakov Cement** with up to 20% slag replacement of **CEM II/A-S 42.5 N**. The hardened concrete was impregnated with **methyl methacrylate (MMA)**. These specific materials were used in the experiments because the samples made from them demonstrated significantly higher performance.

Figure 1. Dependence of the compressive strength of polymer concrete on the impregnating polymer.

Due to the high cost of the organic component and the more complex technology, polymer concretes are significantly more expensive materials (by 60–100 %) than the original concrete matrix. Therefore, they are used in cases where the inorganic component alone cannot provide the required properties and durability of structural elements and products.

The most effective application of polymer concretes is in critical structures where high strength, density, and corrosion resistance are required: in the production of tunnel segments (replacing cast iron), for underground transportation structures (e.g., tunnel lining in metro construction), acid-resistant tanks, and high-pressure pipes (as a substitute for metal) [2,3].

Polymer treatment of concrete is advisable for use in severe climatic conditions to enhance durability, as well as for protection against radioactive radiation, gas and liquid aggression, and for producing electrically insulating and wear-resistant composites, such as in airfield pavements, nuclear power plant construction, and other critical facilities.

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